

A Statistical Study of Warm Plasma Cloak Particles Using Van Allen Probe Data

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Additional Supporting Information (Files uploaded separately)

Table S1: Warm Plasma Cloak (WPC) event list for H⁺ ions.

Table S2: WPC event list for O⁺ ions.

Table S3: Identified Plasmopause locations.

Introduction

- The supporting information document provides complete list of WPC events observed for both H⁺ and O⁺ ions using Van Allen Probe-A satellite.
- All three table files added in this document include event list as well as corresponding L-shell and MLT locations of satellite.
- The WPC list file also include minimum and maximum energies for each event. Within these Min-Max energies, particles have dominant bidirectional flow compared to perpendicular flow.